

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

EXPERIENCE IN TEACHER TRAINING TO OVERCOME LEARNING LOSSES IN THE SECONDARY SCHOOL DUE TO THE WAR IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

The author analyzes survey data involving participants in projects aimed at overcoming learning losses. The article emphasizes the importance of preparing teachers for tutoring support and demonstrates a teacher training program, highlighting the importance of methodological support for teachers such as supervision. Results of a survey answered by teachers are analyzed in the article, and conclusions are drawn about the necessity of providing tutors with methodological and socio-psychological support when working with students who have learning losses.

Keywords: tutor, tutoring support, learning losses, supervision.

In the conditions of a state of war, intensive searches for new approaches to education, innovative forms of organizing the educational process, and effective pedagogical technologies are taking place. Research indicates a decrease in the number of students possessing skills necessary for independent learning: time management, organizing their work, independently completing tasks, self-assessment. Therefore, compensating for learning losses through self-study of educational material may be ineffective for some students. Considering that a large number of children in Ukraine are studying remotely, tutoring support becomes increasingly important for successful learning. Tutors can support students in various aspects of learning: the ability to learn independently, maintaining motivation for learning, promoting psycho-emotional stability.

The experience of projects by civil society organizations aimed at overcoming educational losses, including NGOs such as "Teach for Ukraine," "Osvitoria," "EdCamp Ukraine," "Education 360," "Tech StartUp School," funded by international donors, indicates that due to teacher-tutors, it is possible not only to make up for knowledge gaps but also to provide social-emotional support to students. A study conducted by the Vox Populi agency from July to September 2023, commissioned by the organization "Teach for Ukraine" with the support of the international humanitarian organization Save the Children, involving 2231 students aged 14 and up, as well as their parents and 825 educators, showed that 68–75% of students studied for 20 hours a week, while others studied less. Students from frontline areas, especially in Dnipropetrovsk region, suffer the most significant learning losses. Parents rate the quality of education as unsatisfactory. The complexity of the problem encompasses security, technical means, lack of printed textbooks, cancellation or rescheduling of classes. Parents of children primarily engaged in online learning mention a loss of motivation for learning, worsening self-discipline, poor self-learning skills [2].

The largest project in Ukraine aimed at compensating for educational losses, implemented by the NGO

"Teach for Ukraine," is the "Educational Soup" (short for "Educational Support"), which has been ongoing since April 2022. It involves not only free classes following the school curriculum to overcome educational losses for students in grades 5–11 but also providing tutoring support to children. The project's features include: socio-emotional support for children in small groups (3–5 people); academic tutoring for children who often have no contact with their class teacher, their favorite teacher, or other authoritative adults due to the war; assistance in studying core subjects of the school curriculum; conducting regular surveys among tutors and students. The average increase in knowledge among children who participated in this program in 2022 from each subject is 15–17% (according to student testing results). According to parents and children, the most significant positive impact is on students' well-being (<https://teachforukraine.org/project/osvitnij-sup/>).

To provide professional assistance, support, and guidance to children, over 600 teachers have been trained in tutoring competencies. The training program consists of 16 training hours and weekly supervision sessions for teacher-tutors. The focus of the teacher training program "Teacher with Tutoring Competencies" is the development of professional competencies (subject knowledge, teaching methodologies and techniques); formation of common skills for key competencies defined in Article 12 Part 1 of the Law of Ukraine "On Education"; psychological and physiological characteristics of learners of a certain age, basics of andragogy; language, communication, emotional, and ethical competency.

The aim of the program is to enhance the methodological and practical level of professional competence of teachers in developing skills for socio-emotional learning, creativity, communication, teamwork, cooperation, and interactive methods in the context of a state of war. The educational course aims to improve knowledge of theoretical and methodological foundations for developing skills to create a varied educational environment in lessons with an individualized approach

(organization and creation of differentiated tasks at various levels, fostering a learning-developmental atmosphere, instilling in students responsibility for their own education according to their age capabilities, developing study skills, self-awareness, identifying strengths and developing skills to use them, setting and achieving personal goals, ability to reflect on their actions, honing skills to work with various sources of information).

The list of competencies that teachers improve on and acquire includes: mastery of systemic knowledge about the skills of a teacher with tutoring competencies and prospects for their development in the conditions of the New Ukrainian School; ability to operate with terminology describing the principles and approaches of tutoring; ability to apply methods and techniques for developing socio-emotional support skills in the educational process; ability to design, develop, and conduct lessons aimed at developing students' learning skills, self-reflection, identifying their own needs, controlling their emotional state, planning their activities, achieving personal goals, identifying and effectively using their own strengths, working with various sources of information.

To ensure continuous psychological and methodological support for teacher-tutors, group supervision sessions are held weekly. During these sessions, real cases of teaching and tutoring practices are analyzed, mini-trainings on mastering tutoring techniques are conducted, and psychological support is provided to tutors. Supervisory meetings are conducted using a pre-filled form containing a questionnaire about the tutor's emotional state, and the satisfaction level with their activities throughout the week: difficulties and successes are recorded, and tutors also identify current issues for discussion within the tutor circle, supported by trainers and psychologists.

At the end of each 8-week educational support project for students, a final survey of teachers is conducted using the "Tutor Competence Sheet," which documents teachers' self-assessment before and after participation in the project. A total of 113 teachers participated in the survey. Age distribution: 71.1% aged 30 to 49; 20.4% aged 50 to 59; 4.4% aged 25 to 29; others were younger than 25 and older than 59. Teachers from public secondary schools: 52.2% in urban areas, 30.1% in rural areas. 17.7% were involved in the private education sector. During their participation in the project, teacher-tutors not only conducted lessons but also tutoring sessions (tutorials) – 79.6% of project participants. Self-assessment was conducted on a 10-point scale, where 1 was the lowest rating of their competencies and 10 was the highest.

The questions used in the questionnaire and the analysis of changes in self-assessment are presented below. Question 1: Can I apply active listening in working with students? At the beginning of the project, 38.9% of teachers indicated that they could apply active listening from 7 points and above. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 99.1% of teacher-tutors. Interviews with participants allowed us to identify the reasons for this increase in the ability to apply active listening: firstly, constant practice in everyday work allowed for quickly mastering the theoretical material

and applying it in practice; secondly, the rapid positive response of students to the teacher's ability to listen and establish dialogical relationships through active listening.

Question 2: Can I adapt lessons to individual needs and inclinations? At the beginning of the project, 64.6% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they could adapt lessons to the individual needs and inclinations of students. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 99.3% of teacher-tutors. At the beginning of the tutor competency training, teachers noted that they often could not recognize individual student needs and adapt lessons to them. They expressed the opinion that such an approach in group work could not be effective and was only important in individual work. However, mastering individualization tools demonstrated a different dynamic.

Question 3: Can I create a sense of security in teacher-student relationships through I-communication, agreed rules, and nonviolent communication? At the beginning of the project, 62% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they could apply the non-violent communication technique. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 100% of teacher-tutors. As in the previous question, it is noted that teachers were not well versed in the philosophy and techniques of nonviolent communication. However, continuous learning and practice proved that such a skill can be developed in a relatively short time.

Question 4: Is my cooperation with students accompanied by energy and enthusiasm? At the beginning of the project, 67.2% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they felt enthusiasm during their work as tutors. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 100% of teacher-tutors. Teachers' self-assessment data vividly demonstrated that training and support for teachers in supervisions helped them feel more energetic in their work. Additionally, understanding their own needs and values and their ability to satisfy them also positively influenced job satisfaction.

Question 5: Do students trust me? At the beginning of the project, 83.9% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they felt trusted by their students. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 100% of teacher-tutors. Trust questions were tested based on how students react to the teacher, whether they are willing to share their thoughts with tutors, both negative and positive, whether they ask questions, and whether they are willing to defend their opinions without fear of not being accepted by adults. Teacher-tutors noted a tendency where the first three sessions, as a rule, were mostly dedicated to establishing trusting teacher-student relationships, and during further work, the teacher-tutor relationship strengthened.

Question 6: Can every opinion expressed by a student count on attentive listening? At the beginning of the project, 87.6% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they could demonstrate attentive listening to students' thoughts. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 100% of teacher-tutors. Teachers noted that at the beginning of the project, not everyone was ready to accept another opinion, espe-

cially if it did not coincide with the tutor's beliefs. During the project, teacher-tutors learned through active listening, nonviolent communication, the ability to recognize students' needs and values, to take a neutral position, and to understand the meaning of what students say, even if the form of expression did not always correspond to what the student actually felt. Teachers noticed a shift in this aspect thanks to feedback from students participating in the Education Soup. During interviews, students noted that they felt their significance for the first time, that they were heard and understood.

Question 7: Can I provide my students with specific feedback, pointing out the positive aspects of their activities? At the beginning of the project, 68.2% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they could provide students with constructive feedback. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 98.1% of teacher-tutors. The dynamics in this question demonstrated the mastery of the ability to provide specific feedback to students, based on facts, to focus on what works and what needs improvement, to highlight students' strengths and how they can use them to improve their results.

Question 8: Do I know the strengths and weaknesses of my students and can I take this into account in my pedagogical activities? At the beginning of the project, 79.7% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they could recognize the strengths and weaknesses of their students and take this into account when organizing the educational process. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 99% of teacher-tutors. Specific tutoring tools for working with students' strengths helped teachers identify their students' strengths and weaknesses, adjust the educational process accordingly. Teachers noted that they had never thought before about relying more on what students do better (according to M. Seligman) [3]. Building the educational process considering students' strengths and weaknesses contributed not only to improving students' academic performance but also to establishing positive relationships between students and teachers.

Question 9: Can I uncover my students' internal motivation and strengthen it? At the beginning of the project, 66.4% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they could uncover students' internal motivation and support it throughout their participation in the project. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 93.7% of teacher-tutors. The question of student motivation to learn is perhaps the most acute today. In the teacher training program for tutoring competencies, a separate block was dedicated to the issue of student motivation. Practicing the theoretical foundations of maintaining student motivation in practice helped some students feel more motivated to learn and develop themselves. Teachers also noted that understanding the internal factors of motivation helped them feel more tuned to working with students and their own self-development.

Question 10: Can I support and develop student self-discipline? At the beginning of the project, 71.8% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they could support and develop student self-discipline. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by

97.3% of teacher-tutors. One of the directions of work with students was to increase their level of independence in learning and self-regulation. As the dynamics showed, teachers noted that they succeeded in this. During interviews, they mentioned that certain tools for supporting and developing student self-discipline (setting their own educational goals, ability to plan their activities, maintain motivation, understand and use their own resources, ability to overcome obstacles) were especially useful for both students and teachers. It is important to note that project participants practiced these skills on themselves, developing their soft competencies.

Question 11: Can I help students set ambitious and realistic goals? At the beginning of the project, 68.8% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they could help students set goals. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 96.5% of teacher-tutors. Responses to this question demonstrated an increase in teachers' ability to help students not only set goals but also formulate them correctly, check them for compliance with values and ways to achieve them. Teachers used coaching methodologies such as SMART, GROW, goal mapping, and so on.

Question 12: Do students have space for autonomy in my lessons? At the beginning of the project, 68.2% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they could create opportunities for independent work by students during lessons. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 95.5% of teacher-tutors. At the beginning of the training, teachers mentioned that they more often used a traditional approach to teaching, where the teacher presents information. During the course, teachers studied innovative teaching methods aimed at students' independent mastery of the material with the support of the teacher as a facilitator and moderator of the educational process. The tutoring approach, namely: giving students the opportunity to choose, taking responsibility for their choice, trying their hand at different types of activities, proved to be effective teaching methods.

Question 13: Can I maintain a good balance between implementing a complex plan and adapting to what is happening during the lesson? At the beginning of the project, 74.3% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they could maintain a balance between the plan and its implementation. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 98.3% of teacher-tutors. One of the requirements of the modern educational process in conditions of war is the ability of teachers to be flexible and respond promptly to students' needs, to adapt to changing conditions during lessons.

Question 14: Do I give myself time for self-reflection? At the beginning of the project, 58.4% of teachers indicated from 7 points and above that they have time and consciously practice self-reflection. At the end of the project, the same scores were noted by 92.9% of teacher-tutors. Teachers' ability to self-reflect is one of the important components of preventing fatigue from the educational process, burnout, etc. Therefore, during tutoring supervisions, great attention was paid to teachers' self-reflection.

Thus, the data analysis indicates a significant increase in self-assessment of their own tutoring competencies among teacher-tutors. Participants appreciated the importance of supervisions for teacher-tutors: they found them very valuable (84.1%), valuable (15%), and only 1 person considered them insignificant for themselves (0.9%). It is also worth noting that 98.2% of teachers indicated that they apply the knowledge, skills, and experience gained in working with students; 1.8% of participants intend to use them partially.

Working in small groups with a teacher-tutor is an opportunity to structure educational material taking into account students' learning gaps, considering their current requests and needs as much as possible. This work focuses on taking responsibility for one's own education according to age capabilities, forming the skill of learning, identifying and achieving one's own goals, and being able to work with various sources of information.

The educational process is organized in such a way that the first week is always primarily diagnostic and introductory: getting acquainted, establishing trustful relationships, mastering the basic aspects of working with students in the context of tutoring (developing personal learning and development roadmaps, selecting optimal resources to overcome learning gaps). Throughout all weeks, the main task of the tutor is to promote a learning and developmental atmosphere (tutoring sessions), group reflection (checking previously planned activities and results, noting successes and summarizing the day's learning). Tutors help students develop a personal learning roadmap, promote goal-setting and goal achievement planning skills, self-reflection, working with sources, and conduct a brief individual conversation with each student weekly about personal goals and requests. Communication with parents is facilitated through program administrators, and tutors submit a written mini-report to those responsible for maintaining contact with parents weekly. There is also a simplified journal keeping system (list of topics and students' progress tracking). The program does not involve grading and homework.

Over the course of two years of war in Ukraine, surveys of students and parents have allowed for the documentation of positive results from tutoring support for students, including improvements in their emotional state, academic success, increased motivation for learning, and future orientation. Interviews with a focus group of teacher-tutors have shown that all participants

positively evaluate their personal and professional experience with involvement in the Education HUB project and note the beneficial impact of the project itself on school-age children in wartime conditions. Parent responses in the conducted survey indicate that the Education HUB project format allowed them to realize that online education can be effective and motivating. In fact, children's participation in the project has shown that biases against online formats or previous negative experiences with such learning can be corrected through the appropriate application of innovative pedagogical technologies, including tutoring, which have proven themselves well in distance learning.

In summary, it can be argued that overcoming educational losses among Ukrainian students is possible through various strategies. However, teacher preparation for the implementation of individualization, various tutoring approaches, as well as providing them with ongoing professional support and assistance, is one of the necessary directions of state policy. Today, more and more organizations are implementing teacher training specifically aimed at mastering strategies and tactics for overcoming learning losses, and it is not only about students' academic knowledge, but also about their psychosocial well-being. The challenge that arises during teacher training is a change in their mindset: mastering growth mindset (according to C. Dweck) [1]; the ability to adapt and modify educational materials according to the emotional state and needs of students; mastering skills to teach students to learn independently; providing clear instructions to students; maintaining their motivation; treating student mistakes as part of learning; constantly providing opportunities for choice, supporting student autonomy in the educational process; flexibility and mobility of the teacher themselves.

References

1. Dweck C. *Mindset: the New Psychology of Success*. Ballantine Books; 2016.
2. "Educational needs of schoolchildren in the front-line regions of Ukraine": A comprehensive sociological study. URL: <https://osvita.ua/doc/files/news/904/90461/Doslidzheniya-SUP-ukr.pdf> (дата звернення 02.11.2023 р.)
3. Seligman, M. E. P., & Csikszentmihalyi, M. (2000). Positive psychology: An introduction. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 5–14.